

REVIEW article

Adverse outcome pathways: A mechanistic framework for predictive toxicology and risk assessment

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Abstract: The greatest health care and pharmaceutical problems remain adverse drug reactions and chemical toxicities. Because of the extensive use of animal testing, conventional toxicology approaches often do not have the mechanistic insights required to relate molecular perturbations to their adverse biological outcomes. To address this limitation, adverse outcome pathway architecture is a sequence of causally related events beginning with a molecular initiating event, followed by key events, and concluding with an adverse outcome. This study describes the construction and applications of adverse outcome pathways in chemical risk assessment, predictive toxicology, and regulatory decision-making. More recent developments, including quantitative adverse outcome pathways and adverse outcome pathway networks, have enhanced the ability to model biological complexity and dose-response interactions. Adverse outcome pathways provide a solid mechanistic basis for toxicity prediction and allow the transition of modern toxicology to non-animal, human-relevant testing systems, although barriers such as a lack of quantitative data and regulatory acceptability stand.

Introduction

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are a major clinical and toxicological concern [1, 2]. The WHO defines an ADR as a response to a drug that is unintended and noxious at doses typically administered to humans to prevent, diagnose, or treat an illness [3]. By connecting molecular disruptions to clinical outcomes, adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) enhance predictive toxicology and lessen the need for animal testing. ADRs are primarily divided into type A and type B, broadly differentiated by various parameters (**Table 1**) [4, 5].

Table 1: Classification of adverse drug reactions

Type	Name	Description	Examples
A	Augmented	Dose-dependent	Anticoagulants leading to bleeding
B	Bizarre	Not dose-dependent	Hypersensitivity to anticonvulsants
C	Chronic (Chemical)	Due to long-term drug use	Hepatotoxicity caused by paracetamol
D	Delayed	Could arise due to accumulation	Teratogenicity due to phenytoin during pregnancy
E	End-of-use	Withdrawal effects	Rebound hypertension after stopping clonidine
F	Failure	Unexpected failure of therapy	Antimicrobial resistance, oral contraceptive failure
G	Genetic	Genetic variations in enzymes, transporters, etc.	Stevens-Johnson syndrome due to the HLA-B1502 allele with carbamazepine
H	Hypersensitivity	Immune-mediated responses	Serum sickness
I	Immunological	Hypersensitivity reactions	Anaphylaxis, delayed rash.

In **Figures 1-4**, Adverse drug reactions may also be categorized by severity, time of onset, and predisposing factors [6-10].

Figure 1: Classification of adverse drug reactions

Figure 2: Adverse drug reactions classified based on severity

Figure 3: Adverse drug reactions classified based on time

Figure 4: Miscellaneous adverse drug reactions

Toxic reactions and mechanistic perceptions: Toxicity is the ability of a substance to cause harm, which is usually dose-dependent and influenced by the duration of exposure and biological variability [11]. These reactions can be experienced in three broad situations: supratherapeutic doses, therapeutic doses in metabolism of altered conditions, and cumulative exposure (**Figure 5**) [12, 13].

Figure 5: Toxic reactions and types

Drug-induced toxicity: **Figure 6** shows that the interactions between the drug, the biological system, and the host factors such as genetics and metabolism are complex and lead to toxicity [4, 13].

Figure 6: Mechanisms of drug-induced toxicity

Pharmacokinetic-based toxicity: The alterations in the parameters (ADME) increase tissue concentrations and enhance toxic potential (**Figure 7**). So, drug interactions in the inhibition of CYP450, e.g., ketoconazole, lead to a high concentration of warfarin, and hence, it will cause bleeding complications [14-18].

Figure 7: Toxicity based on pharmacokinetic parameters

Pharmacodynamic-based toxicity: Due to overstimulation of the receptor at the intended receptor sites or even in the transmission of the signal pathway, provided the drug exists at its therapeutic range level, **as shown in Figure 8** [19]. Examples: Bradycardia caused by the action of beta-blockers, respiratory depression caused by opioids [4, 19].

Figure 8: Toxicity based on pharmacodynamic parameters

Cellular mechanisms of toxicity: *Apoptosis:* Doxorubicin cardiotoxicity by mitochondrial means. *Necrosis:* Membrane rupture and inflammation (acetaminophen hepatocellular necrosis). *Mitochondrial dysfunction:* oxidative phosphorylation inhibition (valproic acid toxicity) [20], **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Drug-induced cellular damage process

Immunotoxicity and drug-induced hypersensitivity reactions: Drugs may act as haptens, triggering immune-mediated hypersensitivity reactions, **Figure 10**, [21, 22].

Figure 10: Drug-induced hypersensitivity reactions

Antidotes and mechanisms of action: An antidote overcomes the influence of a poison or a toxic substance. Numerous processes of antidotes have been shown in **Figure 11**, [23, 24].

Figure 11: Mechanisms of different types of antidotes

Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs): An AOP is an analytical construct that characterizes a causally related chain of events of varying degrees of biological organization that results in an ecotoxicological effect. The key factor in a toxicological knowledge framework under construction to aid in the chemical risk assessment using mechanistic reasoning is AOPs, and the sequential flow of AOP, using multiple components, **Figure 12**, [25, 26].

Figure 12: Flow of adverse outcome pathway

Adverse outcome pathways provide a mechanistic framework linking molecular interactions to adverse biological outcomes, thereby improving toxicity understanding and risk assessment [27-29]. *Mechanistic insight:* Replaces black-box models by identifying causal biological pathways of toxicity [27, 29]. *Alternative to animal testing:* Supports new approach methodologies for non-animal toxicology [27, 28]. *Risk assessment:* Enhances regulatory decision-making through Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) [28, 29]. *Hazard identification:* Enables early detection of key events for prioritization and regulation of chemicals [27, 28]. *Evolution and global efforts:* The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, OECD's AOP development programme (2012-2025) has standardized AOP construction. The AOP-Wiki and eAOP Portal are world databases on collaborative development and provide the transparency and reproducibility of mechanistic toxicology [27, 28]. *Quantitative AOPs (qAOPs):* They can even be used to predict dose-response relationships in combination with exposure data. Recent advances have pushed AOPs to a quantitative domain, including dose response information and probabilistic modelling as a predictor of the probability of certain outcomes [27, 29]. The OECD AOP Knowledge Base, including AOP-Wiki and eAOP Portal, supports data sharing, pathway development [27, 28], eAOP Portal [28, 30], and AOP Wiki standardization (**Figure 13 - 15**) [27-29].

Figure 13: Adverse outcome pathways-knowledge base

Figure 14: Adverse outcome pathways-knowledge base in association with certain tools

Figure 15: Adverse outcome pathway WIKI portal

Regulatory authorities: *International cooperation and collaboration with the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, OECD:* The OECD and Effectopedia are to facilitate mechanistic toxicology and chemical risk assessment to promote interoperability, enabling the sharing and interoperability of data among researchers (Figure 16) [28, 30].

Figure 16: Actions of components in the adverse outcome pathway framework

U.S. Environmental protection agency (EPA): The EPA has been developing more and more of the use of AOP, which seeks to enhance environmental and chemical risk assessment using mechanistic data and high-throughput screening tools (Figure 17) [31]. These consequences can be human health effects or effects on human survival, growth, and reproduction of wildlife species [29, 31].

European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) and European Chemicals Agency (ECHA): The European agencies EFSA and ECHA use AOP-based frameworks, endocrine disruption and carcinogenicity [30] are some of the key mechanistic events resulting in toxic effects and are collected as a database at the EFSA website, where supportive tools like ML accompany the systematic review and critical examination of *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies [32].

Biological Pathway

Figure 17: Representation of adverse outcome pathways as a biological pathway by Environmental protection agency

Figure 18: European Food Safety Authority website

Case studies are represented for illustrating an AOP application: Aromatase inhibition that results in reproductive dysfunction in fish: This AOP was officially accepted as AOP #23 by the OECD [7, 29]. Female fish inhibition of Aromatase decoys fecundity. *Chemical Stressor:* Fadrozole, a non-steroidal aromatase inhibitor that is used in the treatment of breast cancer. AOP Sequence (**Figure 19**).

Figure 19: Flowchart of aromatase inhibition leading to reproductive dysfunction in fish

The regulatory bodies, like the USEPA and OECD, have extensively applied it in the screening of environmental chemicals and identification of hazards [27, 29, 32]. Covalent protein binding and resulting liver injury (drug-induced liver injury-DILI): The acetaminophen overdose is a classic example used in mechanistic toxicology and development of AOP [14, 32]. Covalent binding of reactive metabolite hepatocellular death liver failure chemical stressor: Acetaminophen (paracetamol) at overdose levels, AOP sequence (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Flowchart of covalent protein binding leading to liver injury-DILI

Adverse outcome pathway can be applied here as it allows the prediction of hepatotoxic potential at an early stage during the preclinical development of drugs [12, 30]. Interventions to prevent ADRs and toxic outcomes: Various interventional strategies are usually adopted to minimize the frequency of ADRs and toxic consequences, as follows: Pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting systems, dose optimization and therapeutic monitoring, rational drug design and toxicological screening, and electronic prescribing and decision-support tools.

Evaluation of key event relationships (KERs) in the AOP framework: The KERs link molecular perturbations to adverse outcomes [27, 29], which include: Biological plausibility: It indicates the logical and scientific plausibility of the connection between two important events, which are consistent to the current body of biological knowledge and on molecular biological, toxicological and physiological evidence to see that the downstream occurrence is a reasonable outcome of the upstream change. Essentially, it determines the degree of importance of a particular event to the occurrence of other outcomes. The essentiality is highly supported with experimental studies involving genetic knockouts, enzyme/pathway blockers that inhibit the subsequent key event. Empirical support is supported by empirical data, which shows a consistent, measurable, time-dependent relationship between events in studies, species, or dose ranges. Together, these three elements-plausibility, essentiality, and empirical evidence-determine how confident researchers and regulators can be in an AOP's validity, guiding its acceptance in predictive toxicology and risk assessment [28, 29].

Limitations and doing business with AOP-based toxicology: Although the AOP paradigm represents a promising move towards mechanistic toxicology and predictive modelling, there are scientific, technical, and regulatory challenges to it, and elimination of these challenges is key to the wider application of AOP-based

methods in toxicological studies and regulatory decision-making [27-29]. Incomplete biological information: Incomplete biological understanding limits linkage between molecular events and outcomes [27]. Example: Unknown downstream consequences of some disruptions of metabolic enzymes [27].

Lack of quantitative data (qAOPs): qAOPs, which link dose-response and time-course data, are still in early development and require extensive experimental and modelling efforts [29].

Single chemical and pathway focus: Many AOPs characterize highly simplistic, linear pathways that are in relation to a single chemical stressor and a distinct endpoint. Thus, it needs to develop AOP networks that can capture biological complexity [29].

Validation and regulatory acceptance: Regulatory agencies may be reluctant to conduct risk evaluations based on untested or developing AOPs. So, formal validation procedures, increased standardization, and additional real-life case studies are required [28, 29].

Problems of data sharing and harmonization: The lack of centralized, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data sets is a disadvantage for AOP development [28].

Resource-intensive development: AOPs development and validation involve the use of interdisciplinary efforts, skills in molecular biology, toxicology, computational modelling, and risk assessment. Formal endorsement, as conducted by international regulatory bodies, might be time-consuming and lead to delays in the use of AOP-based tools [29].

Future preferences and future research: The future directions will entail better scientific depth, technical usefulness, and regulatory integration [27-29].

AOP Networks (AOPNs) development: Replacement of linear AOPs with networked AOPs to increase their ability to model the complexity of biological systems [27].

Advancements in qAOPs: qAOPs will assist the regulators in establishing chemical safety thresholds with more precision. Introduction objective: The objectives are to close the divide between mechanistic science and regulatory dose-setting [29].

Combination with omics and artificial intelligence technologies: The new technologies, which include genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, will be of great benefit to AOP development as they can deliver high-throughput data that can point out new key events and biomarkers of toxicity [27, 28].

The regulatory acceptance and standardisation: Ongoing standardisation attempts by OECD, US EPA, and EU officials, AOP documentation (via AOP-Wiki). Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) Use. Prolonged use of AOPs in risk-based decision-making. Training, outreach, and interdisciplinary collaboration: Future success will rely on learning and competence development in the field of toxicogenomics, systems biology, and computational modelling.

Global collaboration and open science: Cooperation in the world and free science, International harmonization of AOPs with shared databases (AOP-KB, Effectopedia) and shared development of AOPs. *Initiative:* AOP-Wiki, community-based and collaborative tools of OECD [28].

Conclusion: The paradigm shift from conventional, observational toxicology to a mechanistic and predictive science is shown by the adverse outcome pathway concept. Adverse outcome pathways offer a clear and organized method of comprehending toxicity at the molecular, cellular, and organismal levels by outlining the sequential connections between molecular initiating events, key events, and adverse outcomes. In line with international ethical standards and the 3Rs-replacement, reduction, and refinement, this systems-based approach not only increases the biological relevance of safety testing but also dramatically lowers reliance on animal experiments. With the active participation of international regulatory bodies, including the U.S. EPA,

European Chemicals Agency, and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, adverse outcome pathways are becoming more widely acknowledged as a fundamental component of next-generation chemical and pharmaceutical assessment frameworks. Adverse outcome pathways represent a shift toward mechanistic and predictive toxicology by linking molecular events to adverse outcomes. Integration with *quantitative* adverse outcome pathways, AI, and regulatory frameworks will enhance their application in drug safety and risk assessment.” In the end, industry, academics, and regulators must work together to standardize procedures, improve data exchange, and advance mechanistic validation if adverse outcome pathway implementation is to be successful. Adverse outcome pathways have the potential to transform evidence-based toxicology through these collaborative developments, guaranteeing safer treatments, better environmental protection, and better public health outcomes in the future.

References

1. Sherif FM. Role of the pharmacist in adverse drug reaction monitoring. *Pharmacy and Pharmacology International Journal*. 2017; 5(5):133. doi: 10.15406/ppij.2017.05.00133
2. Sherif FM, Sherif RF, Saeed NM. Pharmacotherapy and associated risk factors for pulmonary tuberculosis. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2021; 1(4): 84-49. doi: 10.528/zenodo.5806168
3. Jiang H, Lin Y, Ren W, Fang Z, Liu Y, Tan X, et al. Adverse drug reactions and correlations with drug-drug interactions: A retrospective study of reports from 2011 to 2020. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2022; 13: 923939. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2022.923939
4. Pirmohamed M. Mechanisms of adverse drug reactions. In: Strom BL, Kimmel SE, Hennessy S. *Textbook of Pharmacoepidemiology*. Chichester (UK): John Wiley & Sons; 2nd ed, 2014; 459-474. doi: 10.1002/9781118820186ch30
5. Rawlins MD, Thompson JW. Mechanisms of adverse drug reactions. In: Davies DM. *Textbook of Adverse Drug Reactions*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 1st ed, 1977; 10-31. doi: 10.2165/00002018-200528100-00003
6. Pirmohamed M, James S, Meakin S, Green C, Scott AK, Walley TJ, et al. Adverse drug reactions as cause of admission to hospital: Prospective analysis of 18820 patients. *British Medical Journal*. 2004; 329(7456): 15-19. doi: 10.1136/bmj.329.7456.15
7. World Health Organization. *Safety monitoring of medicinal products: Guidelines for setting up and running a pharmacovigilance centre*. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2000.
8. Uppsala Monitoring Centre. *The importance of pharmacovigilance: Safety monitoring of medicinal products*. Uppsala Monitoring Centre; 2002. Available from: <https://who-umc.org/media/16469/the-importance-of-pharmacovigilance.pdf>
9. Tandon VR, Mahajan V, Khajuria V, Gillani Z. Under-reporting of adverse drug reactions: A challenge for pharmacovigilance in India. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*. 2015; 47(1): 65-71. doi: 10.4103/0253-7613.150344
10. Sreeja R, Ramaiah B, Prabhudev BR, Bangi P. Adverse drug reactions: A prospective observational study at a tertiary care hospital. *International Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacology*. 2025; 15(1): 106-111. doi: 10.18203/2319-2003.ijbcp20254160
11. Ahmad GR, Ahmad D, Rajput SA, Khan H, Shammas MA. Reconsidering the scientific validity of the term “non-toxic” in toxicological risk assessment. *Archives of Clinical Toxicology*. 2026; 8(1): 8-10. doi: 10.46439/toxicology.8.046
12. Hayes AW, Kruger CL. *Principles and methods of toxicology*. Boca Raton (FL): CRC Press; 6th Ed., 2014. doi: 10.1201/9781003390008
13. Pognan F, Beilmann M, Boonen HCM, Czich A, Dear G, Hewitt P, et al. The evolving role of investigative toxicology in the pharmaceutical industry. *Nature Reviews of Drug Discovery*. 2023; 22(4): 317-335. doi: 10.1038/s41573-022-00633-x
14. Zanger UM, Schwab M. Cytochrome P450 enzymes in drug metabolism: Regulation of gene expression, enzyme activities, and impact of genetic variation. *Pharmacology and therapeutics*. 2013; 138(1): 103-141. doi: 10.1016/j.pharmthera.2012.12.007
15. Sarrar AM, Rafieda AM, Shaglouf DH, Elshwain WM. Venous and arterial thrombosis during oral contraceptive use in Libyan women. *Mediterranean Journal of Medical Research*. 2025; 2(4): 259-268. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17863440

16. Alhaddad FE, Abuleid KM. Evaluation of adverse effects of AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine after the first dose in Libyan adults: A cross-sectional study. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022; 2(4): 65-69. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7479778
17. Paul SK. Assessment of knowledge and attitude of adverse drug reactions among healthcare professionals in Bangladesh. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2025; 5(2): 70-78. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15275065
18. Aburawi SM, Erhuma ME, Mussa MA. Incidence of agranulocytosis as an adverse effect of antipsychotic drugs in patients with schizophrenia. *Mediterranean Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2022; 2(2): 52-63. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6780500
19. Khonsary SA. Goodman and Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics. *Surgical Neurology International*. 2023; 14: 91. doi: 10.25259/SNI_184_2023.
20. Kudin AP, Mawasi H, Eisenkraft A, Elger CE, Bialer M, Kunz WS. Mitochondrial liver toxicity of valproic acid and its acid derivatives is related to inhibition of α -lipoamide dehydrogenase. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2017; 18: 1912. doi: 10.3390/ijms18091912
21. Pichler WJ. Immune pathomechanism and classification of drug hypersensitivity. *Allergy*. 2019; 74(8): 1457-1471. doi: 10.1111/all.13765
22. Pavlos R, Mallal S, Ostrov D, Pompeu Y, Phillips E. Fever, rash, and systemic symptoms: Understanding the role of virus and HLA in severe cutaneous drug allergy. *Journal of Allergy Clinical Immunology Practice*. 2014; 2(1): 21-33. doi: 10.1016/j.jaip/2013.11.005
23. Hoegberg LCG, Shepherd G, Wood DM, Johnson J, Hoffman RS, Caravati EM, et al. Systematic review on the use of activated charcoal for gastrointestinal decontamination following acute oral overdose. *Clinical Toxicology (Phila)*. 2021; 59(12): 1196-1227. doi: 10.1080/15563650.2021.1961144
24. Nelson LS, Howland MA, Lewin NA, Smith SW, Goldfrank LR, Hoffman RS. *Goldfrank's Toxicologic Emergencies*. 11th ed. 2019; New York: McGraw-Hill. ISBN: 978-0-07-160594-6.
25. OECD. Users' handbook supplement to the guidance document for developing and accessing adverse outcome pathways. Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development; 2018. doi: 10.1787/5jlv1m9d1g32-en.
26. Ankley GT, Bennett RS, Erickson RJ, Hoff DJ, Hornung MW, Johnson RD, et al. Adverse outcome pathways: A conceptual framework to support ecotoxicology research and risk assessment. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*. 2010; 29(3): 730-741. doi:10.1002/etc.34
27. Villeneuve DL, Crump D, Garcia-Reyero N, Hecker M, Hutchinson TH, LaLone CA, Landesmann B, Lettieri T, Munn S, Nepelska M, Ottinger MA, Vergauwen L, Whelan M. Adverse outcome pathway (AOP) development I: Strategies and Principles, *Toxicological Sciences*. 2014; 142 (2): 312-320. doi: 10.1093/toxsci/kfu199
28. OECD. The adverse outcome pathway knowledge base (AOP-KB). Paris: Organisation for economic co-operation and development; 2020. <https://aopkb.oecd.org>
29. Roper C, Tanguay RL. Adverse outcome pathways: Application to predictive toxicology. *Toxicological Sciences*. 2020; 173(2): 215-226. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-813602-7.00040-5
30. Zhao H, Ni P, Zhao Q, Liang X, Ai D, Erhardt S, et al. Identifying the serious clinical outcomes of adverse reactions to drugs by a multi-task deep learning framework. *Communications Biology*. 2023; 6: 870. doi: 10.1038/s42003-023-05243-w.
31. Jaeschke H, Ramachandran A, Chao X, Ding WX. Emerging and established modes of cell death during acetaminophen-induced liver injury. *Archives of Toxicology*. 2019; 93: 3491-3502. doi: 10.1007/s00204-019-02597-1
32. Vinken M, Knapen D, Vergauwen L, Hengstler JG, Angrish M, Whelan M. Adverse outcome pathways: A concise introduction for toxicologists. *Archives of Toxicology*. 2017; 91(11): 3697-3707 doi: 10.1007/s00204-017-2020-z

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